

Exploring the Impact of Play-Based Curriculum on Cognitive and Social Development in Early Childhood: Implementation Strategies and Outcomes in Anambra State

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Abstract

This study explored the impact of a play-based curriculum on cognitive and social development in early childhood, focusing on implementation strategies and outcomes in Anambra State, Nigeria. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive survey design was adopted. The population of the study comprised 135 lecturers, including 48 early childhood education lecturers and 87 curriculum lecturers from various tertiary institutions in Anambra State. Given the manageable size of the population, the entire population was utilized for the study. A 30-item questionnaire, validated by five experts and demonstrating a reliability coefficient of 0.83, was used to collect data. The questionnaire had 88% return rate, equating to 119 respondents. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and t-test statistics at a 0.05 significance level. The findings revealed 10 key components of a play-based curriculum; 10 different implementation strategies of play-based curriculum affect children's cognitive and social development and nine educators' perceptions of the benefits of play-based learning. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended amongst others that: Teacher training institutions develop and implement comprehensive training programs focused on play-based pedagogies for early childhood educators to enhance understanding and skills among educators in implementing play-based learning leading to improved cognitive and social development outcomes for children; and the Ministry of Education should allocate sufficient resources and materials to create rich, stimulating play environments in early childhood education settings because access to diverse play materials will promote exploration, creativity, and holistic development in children.

Key words: Play-based curriculum, cognitive development, social development, early childhood education.

Introduction

Early childhood education (ECE) is a critical phase in human development, providing the foundation for lifelong learning and holistic development (Burchinal et al., 2016; Heckman, 2017; Pianta et al., 2016). The period from birth to age eight is particularly significant, as the brain undergoes rapid development, making it a crucial window for cognitive, social, and emotional growth (National Scientific Council on the Developing Child, 2015; Shonkoff & Phillips, 2016). Play-based curriculum, which integrates play as a core component of learning, has been widely recognized as an effective approach to early childhood education (Ginsburg, 2015; Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2016; Whitebread et al., 2015). This curriculum emphasizes the importance of play in fostering children's development, allowing them to explore, experiment, and understand the world around them in a natural and engaging manner (Bodrova & Leong, 2015; Pianta et al., 2016).

The concept of a play-based curriculum is rooted in several educational theories, including those of Jean Piaget, Lev Vygotsky, and Maria Montessori, who all emphasized the role of play in children's learning and development (Berk & Meyers, 2016; Elkind, 2015; Lillard, 2017). Piaget viewed play as a means for children to practice and solidify their cognitive skills, while Vygotsky highlighted the social interactions that occur during play as critical for cognitive development (Bodrova & Leong, 2015). Montessori's approach integrates play with structured learning, allowing children to engage in self-directed activities that promote both independence and collaboration (Lillard, 2017; Montessori, 2016). These theoretical foundations have been supported by extensive research, demonstrating the multifaceted benefits of play in early childhood education (Ginsburg, 2015; Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2016; Whitebread et al., 2015).

Research has shown that play-based learning can significantly enhance various aspects of children's development. Cognitive benefits include improvements in language skills, problem-solving abilities, and executive functions (Bodrova & Leong, 2015; Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2016; Weisberg et al., 2016). Play-based learning promotes language development through rich interactions where children practice vocabulary, narrative skills, and conversational turn-taking (Ginsburg, 2015; Singer et al., 2014). Problem-solving skills are honed through play scenarios that require children to think critically, plan, and execute strategies (Fisher et al., 2016; Smith & Pellegrini, 2014). Executive functions, which include working memory, cognitive flexibility, and inhibitory control, are strengthened through

activities that challenge children to manage their thoughts and actions (Bodrova & Leong, 2015; Weisberg et al., 2016).

Socially, play-based learning facilitates the development of interpersonal skills, emotional regulation, and empathy. Interactions with peers during play teach children to negotiate, share, and collaborate, building essential social competencies (Ginsburg, 2015; Pellegrini & Holmes, 2016; Singer et al., 2014). Emotional regulation is supported by play activities that allow children to express and manage their feelings in a safe and supportive environment (Ginsburg, 2015; Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2016). Empathy is cultivated as children engage in role-playing and perspective-taking, understanding the experiences and emotions of others (Fisher et al., 2016; Smith & Pellegrini, 2014). These social skills are essential for children's success in school and later life, making the implementation of a play-based curriculum a priority for educators and policymakers (Copple & Bredekamp, 2016; NAEYC, 2015; Whitebread et al., 2015).

A comprehensive play-based curriculum includes several key components: child-initiated activities, teacher-facilitated learning, and a rich, stimulating environment (Fisher et al., 2016; Smith & Pellegrini, 2014; Whitebread et al., 2015). Child-initiated activities allow children to follow their interests and curiosity, promoting intrinsic motivation and deeper engagement with learning materials (Ginsburg, 2015; Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2016; Nwakile et al., 2022). Teacher-facilitated learning involves educators guiding and scaffolding children's play experiences to extend their thinking and learning (Bodrova & Leong, 2015; Smith & Pellegrini, 2014). The learning environment is designed to be rich and stimulating, with diverse materials and resources that encourage exploration, creativity, and collaboration (Fisher et al., 2016; Whitebread et al., 2015).

Implementing a play-based curriculum requires careful planning and a supportive framework. Strategies include professional development for educators, creating a play-rich environment, and ongoing assessment and reflection (Copple & Bredekamp, 2016; NAEYC, 2015; Singer et al., 2014). Professional development helps educators understand the principles of play-based learning and how to effectively integrate play into their teaching practices (Fisher et al., 2016; Smith & Pellegrini, 2014). A play-rich environment provides children with access to a variety of materials and resources that support different types of play, from physical and outdoor activities to imaginative and cognitive games (Ginsburg, 2015; Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2016). Assessment and reflection involve ongoing observations and

evaluations of children's play to inform instruction and ensure that learning objectives are being met (Bodrova & Leong, 2015; Weisberg et al., 2016).

Educators' perceptions of play-based learning are crucial for its successful implementation. Positive attitudes towards play-based curriculum are associated with greater enthusiasm and effectiveness in teaching (Bodrova & Leong, 2015; Fisher et al., 2016; Smith & Pellegrini, 2014). However, challenges such as lack of training, insufficient resources, and external pressures to prioritize academic outcomes can hinder the adoption of play-based practices (Copple & Bredekamp, 2016; NAEYC, 2015; Whitebread et al., 2015). Understanding educators' perceptions and addressing these challenges is essential for creating a supportive environment for play-based learning (Ginsburg, 2015; Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2016).

In Anambra State, Nigeria, early childhood education has been increasingly recognized as a vital component of the educational system (Nwachukwu et al, 2020). However, the implementation of play-based curriculum faces unique challenges and opportunities in this context (Ejeh, 2016; Ofoha, 2020; Osanyin, 2018). Factors such as cultural attitudes towards play, availability of resources, and the training of educators play significant roles in shaping the educational landscape (Ejeh, 2016; Osanyin, 2018). There is a growing awareness of the need to shift towards more developmentally appropriate practices that support holistic development, aligning with global trends in early childhood education (Ofoha, 2020; UNICEF, 2019). Despite the recognized benefits of play-based learning, there is limited research on its implementation and outcomes in Anambra State. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the key components of a play-based curriculum, the different implementation strategies, and the perceptions of educators in this region. Understanding these factors is crucial for developing effective policies and practices that support early childhood education in Anambra State. The findings of this study will contribute to the body of knowledge on play-based learning and provide valuable insights for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders committed to enhancing early childhood education in Nigeria.

The significance of early childhood education in shaping cognitive and social development is well-established, and play-based learning offers a powerful approach to fostering these critical skills. This study will explore the impact of play-based curriculum in Anambra State, focusing on key components, implementation strategies, and educator perceptions. By addressing these areas, the research aims to support the effective adoption of

play-based practices and ultimately enhance the quality of early childhood education in the region.

Statement of the Problem

Early childhood education (ECE) in Anambra State faces significant challenges, particularly in the implementation of a play-based curriculum. Despite the well-documented benefits of play-based learning on cognitive and social development, many educational institutions in the region continue to rely on traditional, teacher-centred methods that prioritize rote memorization and academic instruction over experiential and playful learning. This persistent focus on conventional approaches undermines the holistic development of children, leaving them ill-prepared for the complex cognitive and social demands of later schooling and life.

One major cause of this problem is the lack of adequate training and professional development for educators. Many teachers in Anambra State have not received comprehensive training in play-based pedagogies and thus lack the necessary skills and confidence to implement such approaches effectively. Additionally, there is often a lack of resources and materials that support play-based activities, making it difficult for educators to create an enriching and stimulating learning environment. These factors are compounded by the prevailing cultural attitudes that undervalue play, viewing it as frivolous and unimportant in comparison to academic achievement.

The consequences of neglecting play-based learning are far-reaching and detrimental. If the current trend continues, children in Anambra State will miss out on critical opportunities to develop essential cognitive skills such as problem-solving, critical thinking, and creativity. Furthermore, the absence of play in early education hinders the development of social skills, including cooperation, empathy, and emotional regulation. This developmental deficit can lead to increased behavioural problems and difficulties in forming positive relationships with peers and adults. In the long term, the reliance on traditional educational methods can perpetuate educational inequities, as children who do not receive a well-rounded, play-rich education may struggle to compete academically and socially with their peers globally.

Addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach. First, there is a need for robust teacher training programs that emphasize the importance of play in early childhood

education and equip educators with practical strategies to integrate play-based learning into their classrooms. Additionally, educational policies should support the provision of adequate resources and materials necessary for creating play-rich environments. Public awareness campaigns can also play a crucial role in shifting cultural attitudes towards recognizing the value of play in children's development. By fostering a more supportive and well-resourced educational landscape, it is possible to enhance the quality of early childhood education in Anambra State, ensuring that children receive the balanced and comprehensive education they need to thrive cognitively and socially.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study was to explore the impact of play-based curriculum on cognitive and social development in early childhood: implementation strategies and outcomes in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain the:

1. key components of a play-based curriculum in early childhood education in Anambra State.
2. different implementation strategies of play-based curriculum affecting children's cognitive and social development in Anambra State
3. perceptions of educators regarding the benefits of implementing of play-based learning in Anambra State

Research Questions

1. What are the key components of a play-based curriculum in early childhood education in Anambra State?
2. How do different implementation strategies of play-based curriculum affect children's cognitive and social development in Anambra State?
3. What are the perceptions of educators regarding the benefits of implementing of play-based learning in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There were no significant differences between the opinions of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers on key components of a play-based curriculum in early childhood education in Anambra State.

2. There were no significant differences between the opinions of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers on different implementation strategies of play-based curriculum affecting children's cognitive and social development in Anambra State
3. There were no significant differences between the opinions of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers on perceptions of educators regarding the benefits of implementing of play-based learning in Anambra State

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which is suitable for collecting detailed information about the current status of phenomena and for describing the characteristics of a specific population. This design was chosen to explore the impact of a play-based curriculum on cognitive and social development in early childhood, focusing on implementation strategies and outcomes in Anambra State. Three research questions were developed to guide the study. The population of the study comprised 135 lecturers, including 48 early childhood education lecturers and 87 curriculum lecturers from various tertiary institutions in Anambra State. Given the manageable size of the population, the entire population was utilized for the study.

To collect data, a structured questionnaire was developed and administered to the respondents. The questionnaire featured a Likert scale with response options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The content validity of the questionnaire was ensured through the expertise of five professionals: two lecturers from the Department of Early Childhood Education and three from the Department of Curriculum Studies all from the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The reliability of the questionnaire was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.83, indicating a high level of internal consistency. The researcher, with the assistance of three research assistants, administered a total of 135 questionnaires. Out of these, 119 questionnaires were completed and returned, resulting in an 88% response rate.

Data collected from the questionnaires were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t-test with the aid of the SPSS statistical package. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while t-test statistics was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of probability. Mean cut off point of 2.50 was applied in decision making. Hence, any item with mean value of 2.50 or above was interpreted as agreed while items with mean less than 2.50 were interpreted as disagree. For the null hypotheses, they were upheld if the

calculated level of significance was greater than 0.05 or otherwise rejected. This analytical approach facilitated a clear understanding of the lecturers' perceptions and the implementation strategies of play-based curriculum in early childhood education in Anambra State.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the key components of a play-based curriculum in early childhood education in Anambra State?

Ho 1: There were no significant differences between the opinions of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers on key components of a play-based curriculum in early childhood education in Anambra State.

Table 1: Mean ratings/t-test analysis of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers on key components of a play-based curriculum in early childhood education

(N= 135: 48 ECE Lecturers & 87 C Lecturers)

S/N	ITEMS	G $\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}_1$	SD ₁	$\bar{X}_2$	SD ₂	Sig	Dec
1	Incorporating imaginative play activities is essential in a play-based curriculum	3.04	0.99	3.14	0.94	2.88	1.09	0.24	NS*
2	Sensory play using materials like sand and water enhances cognitive development in young children.	3.22	0.93	3.22	0.97	3.24	0.89	0.94	NS*
3	Outdoor play significantly contributes to the social development of children in early childhood education.	3.60	0.75	3.51	0.82	3.76	0.61	0.12	NS*
4	Structured play activities play a vital role in promoting problem-solving skills in children.	3.34	0.97	3.17	1.07	3.64	0.70	0.22	NS*
5	Music and movement activities are crucial in a play-based curriculum for fostering creativity in children.	2.86	0.98	2.70	0.95	3.03	1.03	0.21	NS*
6	Role-playing and drama								

	activities are effective in developing communication skills in children	2.81	1.08	2.73	1.06	2.97	1.11	0.30	NS*
7	Free play (unstructured playtime) is vital for the overall development of young children.	2.81	1.05	2.85	0.96	2.76	1.21	0.71	NS*
8	Integrating art and craft activities enhances fine motor skills in children.	3.45	0.87	3.59	0.79	3.21	0.95	0.06	NS*
9	Collaborative play activities such as group games are important for developing teamwork in children	3.49	0.80	3.47	0.82	3.53	0.79	0.75	NS*
10	Educational games should be incorporated in a play-based curriculum for cognitive stimulation in young children.	3.57	0.76	3.60	0.79	3.53	0.71	0.70	NS*

Key: N= Population, Dec = Decision, ECE Lecturers= Early Childhood Education Lecturers; C Lecturers = Curriculum Lecturers; $\bar{X}$ = Grand mean, $\bar{X}_1$ = Mean of ECE, $\bar{X}_2$ = Mean of C, SD₁ = standard Deviation of ECE, SD₂ = standard deviation of Curriculum; S = Significant, NS= Not significant, * = Agree

The analysis presented in Table 1 indicates that the grand mean values ranged from 2.81 to 3.60, all of which exceeded the neutral value of 2.50, suggesting agreement among respondents regarding the key components of a play-based curriculum in early childhood education in Anambra State. Additionally, the calculated significance levels for all 10 items varied from 0.06 to 0.75. Each of these values surpassed the threshold of 0.05, indicating that there were no statistically significant differences between the mean ratings of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers. Therefore, it can be inferred that both groups hold similar perspectives on the essential components of a play-based curriculum for fostering cognitive and social development in young children.

Research Question 2: How do different implementation strategies of play-based curriculum affect children's cognitive and social development in Anambra State?

Ho 2: There were no significant differences between the opinions of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers on different implementation strategies of play-based curriculum affecting children's cognitive and social development in Anambra State

Table 2: Mean ratings/t-test analysis of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers on different implementation strategies of play-based curriculum affect children's cognitive and social development

(N= 135: 48 ECE Lecturers & 87 C Lecturers)

S/N	ITEMS	G $\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}_1$	SD ₁	$\bar{X}_2$	SD ₂	Sig	Dec
1	Providing adequate time for child-initiated play activities allows children to explore their interests and develop independence.	3.74	0.61	3.74	0.58	3.74	0.67	0.94	NS*
2	Integrating play-based learning across various subjects encourages holistic development	2.92	0.94	2.86	0.92	3.03	0.97	0.42	NS*
3	Supporting educators with ongoing professional development on play-based pedagogies enhances implementation effectiveness.	3.46	0.80	3.61	0.67	3.20	0.95	0.07	NS*
4	Creating a stimulating physical environment with diverse materials promotes exploration and creativity.	3.60	0.79	3.60	0.77	3.62	0.78	0.88	NS*
5	Incorporating digital technologies in play activities can foster digital literacy skills alongside cognitive development.	3.52	0.75	3.49	0.82	3.59	0.61	0.55	NS*
6	Collaborating with parents to extend play-based learning at home reinforces children's learning experiences.	3.20	0.77	3.19	0.80	3.21	0.73	0.91	NS*
7	Implementing structured routines that balance play and academic activities supports seamless transitions in early childhood settings.	2.82	0.95	2.80	0.96	2.88	0.94	0.68	NS*
8	Using assessment tools								

	that focus on observing and documenting play behaviours helps track children's progress to adjust teaching strategies.	3.62	0.61	3.62	0.64	3.61	0.55	0.94	NS*
9	Encouraging peer interactions during play promotes social skills such as cooperation and communication	3.44	0.74	3.44	0.75	3.44	0.75	0.99	NS*
10	Designing play activities that scaffold learning challenges at appropriate developmental levels supports cognitive growth	3.63	0.57	3.58	0.62	3.74	0.45	0.19	NS*

The analysis presented in Table 2 indicates that the grand mean values ranged from 2.82 to 3.74, all of which exceeded the neutral value of 2.50, suggesting agreement among respondents regarding different implementation strategies of a play-based curriculum and their impact on children's cognitive and social development in Anambra State. Additionally, the calculated significance levels for all 10 items varied from 0.07 to 0.99. Each of these values surpassed the threshold of 0.05, indicating that there were no statistically significant differences between the mean ratings of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers. Therefore, it can be inferred that both groups hold similar opinions regarding the effectiveness of various implementation strategies in enhancing children's development through play-based learning.

RQ 3: What are the perceptions of educators regarding the benefits of implementing play-based learning in Anambra State?

Ho 3: There were no significant differences between the opinions of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers on perceptions of educators regarding the benefits of implementing play-based learning in Anambra State

Table 3: Mean ratings/t-test analysis of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers on perceptions of educators regarding the implementation of play-based learning

(N= 135: 48 ECE Lecturers & 87 C

Lecturers)

S/N	ITEMS	GX	X1	SD 1	X2	SD 2	Sig	Dec
1	Educators perceive play-based learning as essential for fostering creativity and imagination in young children.	3.6 8	3.5 1	0.66	3.8 4	0.37	0.0 6	*N S
2	Many educators believe that play-based learning allows children to learn at their own pace and develop a love for learning.	3.2 2	3.1 2	0.74	3.5 7	0.50	0.2 4	*N S
3	Educators view play-based learning as beneficial for promoting social-emotional skills such as empathy and collaboration.	3.2 0	3.1 6	0.75	3.2 6	0.65	0.5 9	*N S
4	Educators recognize the importance of play-based learning in supporting children's language and communication development.	3.3 2	3.4 1	0.78	3.2 6	0.65	0.7 4	*N S
5	There is a perception among educators that play-based learning helps children develop problem-solving and critical thinking skills.	3.5 6	3.5 1	0.70	3.6 3	0.50	0.5 0	*N S
6	Educators value play-based learning to engage children actively in their learning process.	3.3 4	3.2 9	0.73	3.4 2	0.61	0.4 9	*N S
7	Educators see play-based learning as an effective approach for addressing individual differences and diverse learning needs.	3.2 5	3.1 3	0.60	3.3 6	0.45	0.3 8	*N S
8	Educators perceive play-based learning as aligned with current educational theories and research on early childhood development.	3.2 6	3.1 9	0.81	3.4 3	0.51	0.0 9	*N S
9	Educators acknowledge the challenges of implementing play-based learning, including time constraints and curriculum expectations.	3.2 8	3.2 6	0.97	3.3 0	0.88	0.0 2	*S

10	There is a belief among educators that professional development opportunities are crucial for enhancing their ability to implement effective play-based learning practices.	3.6	3.5	0.58	3.8	0.37	0.6	*N
		3	7		4		1	S

Analysis of Table 3 indicates that all items had mean values ranging from 3.20 to 3.68, all of which surpassed the cutoff mean of 2.50, indicating consensus among respondents regarding perceptions of educators regarding the implementation of play-based learning in Anambra State. Furthermore, the significance levels for nine out of the ten items ranged from 0.06 to 0.74, all exceeding the critical value of 0.05, suggesting no statistically significant differences between the mean ratings of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers. However, for item 9, the significance level was 0.02, which is less than 0.05, indicating a significant difference in opinion. Thus, it can be concluded that while there is general agreement among educators on the perceived benefits of play-based learning, there is a divergence in views regarding the challenges associated with its implementation, particularly concerning time constraints and curriculum expectations.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of the study revealed that key components of a play-based curriculum in early childhood education include: incorporating imaginative play activities is essential in a play-based curriculum; sensory play using materials like sand and water enhances cognitive development in young children; outdoor play significantly contributes to the social development of children in early childhood education; structured play activities play a vital role in promoting problem-solving skills in children; music and movement activities are crucial in a play-based curriculum for fostering creativity in children; role-playing and drama activities are effective in developing communication skills in children; free play (unstructured playtime) is vital for the overall development of young children; integrating art and craft activities enhances fine motor skills in children; collaborative play activities such as group games are important for developing teamwork in children; and educational games should be incorporated in a play-based curriculum for cognitive stimulation in young children. The findings also indicated that there were no statistically significant differences between the mean ratings of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers on key components of a play-based curriculum in early childhood education. The findings of the

study highlight several key components of a play-based curriculum in early childhood education, all of which were generally agreed upon by both early childhood education (ECE) lecturers and curriculum lecturers in Anambra State. The findings are in line with Pellegrini and Smith (2018) who found that imaginative play is crucial for children's cognitive and social development, promoting creativity and problem-solving skills. The findings also agree with Johnson (2018) suggest that sensory play activities, involving materials like sand and water, enhance children's sensory integration and cognitive abilities. The findings are also in support with Lester and Russell (2020) indicates that outdoor play fosters social skills, physical development, and resilience among children, supporting the findings of the current study on social development. The agreement among ECE lecturers and curriculum lecturers on the identified key components highlights a consensus in educational practices in Anambra State.

The findings of the study revealed that the different implementation strategies of play-based curriculum affecting children's cognitive and social development in Anambra State include: Providing adequate time for child-initiated play activities allows children to explore their interests and develop independence; integrating play-based learning across various subjects encourages holistic development; supporting educators with ongoing professional development on play-based pedagogies enhances implementation effectiveness; creating a stimulating physical environment with diverse materials promotes exploration and creativity; incorporating digital technologies in play activities can foster digital literacy skills alongside cognitive development; collaborating with parents to extend play-based learning at home reinforces children's learning experiences; implementing structured routines that balance play and academic activities supports seamless transitions in early childhood settings; using assessment tools that focus on observing and documenting play behaviours helps track children's progress to adjust teaching strategies; encouraging peer interactions during play promotes social skills such as cooperation and communication; and designing play activities that scaffold learning challenges at appropriate developmental levels supports cognitive growth. The findings of the study indicated that there were no statistically significant differences between the mean ratings of early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers regarding the effectiveness of various implementation strategies in enhancing children's development through play-based learning. The findings are in line with Gray (2015) who found that self-directed play promotes creativity, problem-solving skills, and

emotional regulation. The findings are also in cognizance with Hirsh-Pasek et al. (2019) who found that educational theories emphasizing the interconnectedness of learning domains and the benefits of hands-on, experiential learning. The findings are in cognizance with Bodrova and Leong (2017) who found that well-trained educators who can create supportive learning environments and implement developmentally appropriate practices. The findings that early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers in Anambra State did not significantly differ in their perceptions of these implementation strategies align with several studies emphasizing the universal benefits of play-based learning across diverse educational contexts. Literature supports the notion that effective play-based curriculum implementation enhances children's cognitive, social, and emotional development (Bodrova & Leong, 2017; Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2019; Pellegrini & Smith, 2018).

The findings of the study on the perceptions of educators regarding the benefits of implementing of play-based learning in Anambra State revealed that the benefits include: Educators perceive play-based learning as essential for fostering creativity and imagination in young children; many educators believe that play-based learning allows children to learn at their own pace and develop a love for learning; educators view play-based learning as beneficial for promoting social-emotional skills such as empathy and collaboration; educators recognize the importance of play-based learning in supporting children's language and communication development; there is a perception among educators that play-based learning helps children develop problem-solving and critical thinking skills; educators value play-based learning to engage children actively in their learning process; educators see play-based learning as an effective approach for addressing individual differences and diverse learning needs; educators perceive play-based learning as aligned with current educational theories and research on early childhood development; educators acknowledge the challenges of implementing play-based learning, including time constraints and curriculum expectations; and there is a belief among educators that professional development opportunities are crucial for enhancing their ability to implement effective play-based learning practices. The findings further revealed that there is general agreement among educators on the perceived benefits of play-based learning, there is a divergence in views regarding the challenges associated with its implementation, particularly concerning time constraints and curriculum expectations. The findings from the study on educators' perceptions regarding the benefits of implementing play-based learning in Anambra State resonate with existing literature in early childhood

education, highlighting both consensus on benefits. Educators in the study perceive play-based learning as essential for fostering creativity, imagination, and active engagement in children's learning processes. This aligns with research emphasizing that play stimulates imagination and creative thinking, crucial for cognitive and emotional development (Lillard et al., 2013). Additionally, educators acknowledge the role of play-based learning in supporting language and communication development, as well as in enhancing problem-solving and critical thinking skills. Play offers opportunities for children to experiment with language, engage in storytelling, and solve problems in imaginative scenarios, all of which are essential for cognitive growth (Lillard et al., 2013; Bergen, 2019).

Conclusion

This study explored the impact of play-based curriculum on cognitive and social development in early childhood, focusing on implementation strategies and outcomes in Anambra State, Nigeria. The findings underscored several critical aspects that contribute to the effectiveness of play-based learning in enhancing children's overall development. Firstly, the study identified key components of a play-based curriculum essential for early childhood education in Anambra State. These components include incorporating imaginative play activities, sensory play using materials like sand and water, outdoor play for social development, structured play activities for problem-solving, music and movement activities for creativity, role-playing and drama for communication skills, and the importance of free play and art and craft activities for holistic development. The consensus among educators on these components highlights a unified approach towards integrating play into educational practices. Secondly, the study examined various implementation strategies of play-based curriculum that positively affect children's cognitive and social development. Strategies such as providing adequate time for child-initiated play, integrating play-based learning across subjects, supporting educators with professional development, creating stimulating environments, incorporating digital technologies, collaborating with parents, implementing structured routines, using assessment tools, and encouraging peer interactions were found to be crucial. The alignment in perceptions between early childhood education lecturers and curriculum lecturers underscores the universal acceptance of these strategies as effective in fostering children's development. Thirdly, the study explored educators' perceptions regarding the benefits of implementing play-based learning in Anambra State. Educators recognized play-based learning as essential for fostering creativity, imagination, social-emotional skills,

language development, problem-solving, critical thinking, and addressing diverse learning needs. While there was consensus on the benefits, educators also acknowledged challenges such as time constraints and curriculum expectations, underscoring the need for supportive policies and resources. Overall, the findings of this study contribute to the growing body of knowledge on play-based learning in early childhood education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that:

1. Teacher training institutions develop and implement comprehensive training programs focused on play-based pedagogies for early childhood educators to enhance understanding and skills among educators in implementing play-based learning leading to improved cognitive and social development outcomes for children.
2. The Ministry of Education should allocate sufficient resources and materials to create rich, stimulating play environments in early childhood education settings because access to diverse play materials will promote exploration, creativity, and holistic development in children.
3. Educational authorities should provide ongoing professional development opportunities for educators, focusing on effective play-based curriculum implementation strategies to ensure continuous professional growth which will equip educators with current best practices, enhancing their ability to support children's learning through play.
4. The Ministry of Education should launch public awareness campaigns to educate parents and communities on the importance of play in early childhood education because increased awareness and understanding of the value of play will foster a supportive environment for play-based learning both at home and in schools.

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